

Enhancing the security of ATM transaction “an architecture approach”

Opul Sorker¹, Prof. Jahanara Akhtar^{2*}

¹M.S. Student, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Dhaka International University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

²Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering Dhaka International University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Abstract: Nowadays banking service is increasing rapidly day by day. Though the bank renders us plenty of good services, there are also some problems there. Automated Teller Machine (ATM) cards are the good things of the banking system. It is an easy way to withdraw money from the ATM machine by using an ATM card. Even though there is a possibility to hack the ATM card password (PIN) and lose the ATM card. Besides, there are many frauds in our societies especially in banking sectors. The fraudsters can hack our ATM card password or PIN to withdraw money illegally. In this paper, we did full palm scanning to withdraw money without using an ATM card and send a text message to the customer or original bank account holder. In addition, we have also used the password or PIN number of the customer to withdraw money. Full palm scanning, sending a text message, password and not using an ATM card will ensure high security of the bank customer to authenticate the original customer or account holder as well as exchange money.

Keywords: Mobile phone, Security, Palm Scanning, Frauds, Password (PIN), ATM Card.

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Introduction

Biometrics authentication provides different types of advantages over the banking system. To authenticate illegal or frauds, the biometric system is being improved day by day in the current world. Besides, fingerprint, facial and other methods are very popular in the present time. The palm scanning is a highly secure method to authenticate the original customer. The banking services are being improved day by day. Furthermore, the ATM card holders of the banks are also rising in the world so rapidly. However, the number of hackers or bad people is increasing day by day with their different skills in the banking system. There are several types of frauds such as Automated Teller Machine (ATM) card theft, Personal Identification Number (PIN) theft, skimming, card reader techniques and so on. Security plays an important role at banks to protect customers from the different attacks. These measurements are of prime importance when thinking of vulnerabilities. Banks must meet certain standards in order to ensure a safe and secure banking environment for their customers. The vulnerabilities and the increasing wave of criminal activities occur at Automated Teller Machine (ATM), where quick cash is the prime target for criminals rather than at banks themselves. Biometric

increases the security of the banking system for both customers and bankers also [1]. Biometrics offer greater security and convenience than traditional methods of personal recognition. Biometric takes the place of the existing technology in some applications. On the other hand, biometric is the only durable access. Decision makers need to understand the level of security guaranteed through the use of biometric systems and the others can exist between the understanding as well as the reality of the sense of security provided. The biometric system is only one part of an overall identification or authentication process, and the other sides of that process will do the same role in setting its effectiveness [2]. The development of a system that integrates facial recognition technology by using facial recognition software is proposed. The facial recognition software would be used to protect customers as well as other institutions alike from intruders and identity thieves. The automatic teller machine security model would combine a physical access card, a PIN and electronic facial recognition that will go as far as withholding the fraudster's card. The faces would be secured as well as PINs if the technology is used broadly. On the other hand, there is no possibility to mimic the biometric features. The biometric features can be used to do identification and authentication, which card and password or PIN do [3]. Initially, the staff of banks will save the customers information like fingerprints, phone number to open the customer's new account, then the customer only accesses the ATM machine. The working of this ATM machine is when a customer submits fingerprint on the fingerprint scanner when it automatically generates a different 4-digit PIN as a SMS to the mobile of the authorized customer through GSM modem connected to the microcontroller. The password received by the customer and then it should be entered by pressing the keys on the touch screen. After pressing the password it verifies whether it is valid or not that would permit the customer further access [4]. Nowadays, an automatic fingerprint identification system (AFIS) is widely used and in the future AFIS will be more familiar. This is a very important role in forensic and civilian applications such as criminal identification, access control, and ATM card identification. The on-line fingerprint verification system runs two stages: design and implementation like minutiae matching and extraction. Ratha proposed an improved version of the minutiae extraction algorithm which is more reliable as well as faster. Besides, the on-line inkless scanner is used to capture input fingerprint image for extracting implementation. The alignment-based elastic matching algorithm is made for minutiae matching. This algorithm is capable of finding the correspondences between minutia in the input image and the stored template without resorting to the exhaustive search and has the ability of adaptively compensating for the nonlinear deformations and inexact pose transformations between fingerprints. The inkless scanner captures two sets of fingerprint images, which are tested by the system. To be acceptable image accuracy, the verification accuracy is used. Usually, about 8 seconds on a SPARC 20 workstation takes to complete a full fingerprint verification procedure. These empirical results present that the system response time of on-line verification is good with better accuracy [5]. The fingerprint verification of ATM security systems is being used biometrically with hybridization. The fingerprint criterion is selected, because of its availability, reliability, and high accuracy. In the system, the working of this ATM machine is when the customer positions on the fingerprint module when it accesses the ATM to draw the cash, then the machine wants to fingerprint the user's which use the machine. Using biometric, it verifies or identifies fingerprints and gives accurate results if it is valid or not valid. We can prevent the crimes of ATM from the attackers and can secure it in this way [6].

II. Methodology

A. Analysis and proposed biometric (palm scan) strategy for the banking system

Biometric authentication has become more and more popular in the banking system in the decade. The idea of palm scan is not only for ATM security but also to reduce the lack of client understanding on the banking system, especially ATM systems. We proposed the idea of an ATM with a biometric (palm-print or scan), PIN number or password security system for more secure the client's money in the ATM machine in the banking system. In addition, we presented that without using an ATM card (debit/credit or others) the bank user or customer can easily withdraw money from the ATM machine securely.

III. Proposed System Design

In this research paper, we are carried out for the sole purpose of making three factors: authentication metrics such as client’s account number, the PIN number (password) and biometric feature (palm-print or scan) for both card holder and card nominee. It is hoped that the client should occupy a client’s account number, to know and keep in mind his/her PIN number (password), and enter his/her palm-print or palm scanning into the palm scanning device/reader adapter in the system. In the bank, the customers have to open a bank account and register and so forth. The diagram [Fig:-1] is discussed below.

Fig.1. The diagram of the user's banking application system.

In the figure above, we have shown that there are three parts of the banking system such an administrator, bank authority/staff, and bank customer/account holder. Besides, those parts are doing different tasks. The administrator (admin) controls the database server in the banking system. In addition, the administrator also starts and stops the system. On the other hand, open a new account, take a palm scan, a PIN and check the customer balance of the bank account holder by bank authority/staff. However, the bank customer deposits money for his/her own account. The diagram [fig:-2] shows different types of processing between ATM machines and customers or users.

Fig. 2. Processing diagram between ATM machine and user.

In the figure-2 shown, several tasks have been done between the ATM machine and the user. Firstly, the bank customers enter the account number in the ATM machine by using the keypad. Then if the customer's account number is valid then go forward, otherwise go back and try again (maximum 3 times). In addition, submit your palm scanning, if the palm scan is matched then go forward, otherwise go back and try again (maximum 3 times). After that enter the PIN customer PIN number, which is given from the bank. If the password or PIN number is valid or correct then go ahead, otherwise go back and try again (maximum 3 times). Then choose the types of transaction options that you want to do. Besides, if the transaction is done then go forward and get a confirmation message to the customer phone number, otherwise go back to the types of the transaction options. After the transactions are done then exit.

The diagram [figure-3] shows the different working processes in the ATM machine inside. There are three parts in the processing system such as bank account holder, ATM machine, and Database server. The sequence operation diagram is given below.

Fig. 3. Sequence operation diagram among ATM machine, customer and database server.

IV. Proposed Design Architecture

Fig. 4. Proposed architecture design

V. Discussion

There are some advantages and drawbacks of this method. These following are below:

A. Advantages

- (1) Highly secure method: this method uses the palm scanning, PIN number and text message confirmation to do high security to the customer.
- (2) Easy to access: it is easy to access because of that we have to only enter our account number on the ATM machine.
- (3) Without using an ATM card: we do not use cards to withdraw money from the ATM machine.
- (4) Card stolen or lost possibility: there is no possibility to steal or lose the ATM card.

B. Disadvantages

- (1) Process time: it takes a little more time to process the operation.
- Memory capacity: it needs a little more memory space to store the customer information

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